

High Energy Spatial Entropy Utilizing the Correspondence Principle

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In (1), Shannon's spatial entropy is computed using $-\int |W|^2 \ln|W|^2 dx$, where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction and a classical envelope approximation: $W^*(x)W(x) = C/v(x)$, where $v(x)$ is classical velocity, is used (according to the idea of the correspondence principle). A momentum entropy: $-\int dp a(p)a(p) \ln[a(p)a(p)]$ (one dimension) is also calculated. Recently in (2), we argued that one should form Shannon's entropy using the probability $= a(p_1)\exp(ip_1 x) a(p_2)\exp(ip_2 x)$. This leads to the following if one sums the first term over p_1, p_2 and integrates the second over x :

$$\text{Entropy} = \int dx -2W x \frac{d}{dx} W - \int dp a(p)a(-p) \ln[a(p)a(-p)] \quad ((1)) \text{ one dimension}$$

In (1), the spatial entropy is found to behave as $\ln(n)$ for high n whereas for ((2)), spatial entropy is always 1. Thus, there is a very large difference between the two. In (1), a momentum entropy $-a(p)a(p)\ln[a(p)a(p)]$ is added to spatial entropy and in ((1)) a very similar momentum piece appears. For the case of the oscillator, $W(x)$ and $a(p)$ are both Gaussians and so the overall result for entropy from (1) and from this note both behave as $\ln(n)$ when n is large, but the factor of $\ln(n)$ differs. Ours is half as large for the case of a quantum oscillator. For our case, all of the entropy comes from the momentum term in the large n limit.

In this note, we consider these ideas in more detail.

New Entropy Expression

$$\text{Quantum spatial density } W^*(x)W(x) = \sum_{p_1, p_2} a(p_1)a(p_2) \exp(ip_1 x)\exp(ip_2 x) \quad ((2))$$

In (2), we argued that each term in ((2)) i.e. $a(p_1)a(p_2) \exp(ip_1 x)\exp(ip_2 x)$ represents a probability which should be utilized in Shannon's entropy. This leads to an entropy of:

$$\int dx -2W x \frac{d}{dx} W - \int dp a(p)a(-p) \ln[a(p)a(-p)] \quad ((1))$$

where we have used: $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dx \exp(i(x-a)) = 2\pi \delta(x-a)$ with the limits extending from $-\infty$ to ∞ . If one considers $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$, the 2π may be absorbed into $a(p)$ it seems.

Considering the first term: $\frac{d}{dx} (xWW) = WW + x \frac{d}{dx} (WW)$ for W real ((3)).

The first term of ((3)) vanishes at both endpoints. (For the oscillator, $W = c_2 \exp(-axx)$ which drops very rapidly.) Thus, $-\int 2xW \frac{d}{dx} W = \int WW dx$, but the RHS is the spatial density which is normalized to 1, so the spatial entropy is 1 regardless of the wavefunction. Thus, spatial entropy density changes for different wavefunctions (or various excited states), but the overall entropy does not if one uses ((1)). This is a very different result than that obtained using $-\int WW \ln[WW]$.

Correspondence Principle and - WW ln[WW]

In (1), the main idea is to use: $WW=C/v(x)$ to solve: - Integral $WW \ln[WW]$. Here we only provide an outline as the full details are given in (1). The integral becomes:

$$- \text{Integral } dx \ C/v(x) \ln(C/v(x)) \text{ with } C \text{ Integral } dx/v(x)=1 \quad 1/C= \text{Integral } dx/ \sqrt{E-.5kxx}$$

Let $\sqrt{.5k} x = \sqrt{E} \sin(a)$ with $a=0$ to $3.14/2$

Then: $\sqrt{.5m} v(x)= \sqrt{E-.5kxx}= \sqrt{E} \cos(a)$ and $\sqrt{.5k} dx = \sqrt{E} \cos(a) da$ so finally the integral becomes:

$$C \sqrt{.5m} \text{Integral } da \ \ln\{ \ln(\sqrt{E/.5m}) + \ln(\cos(a))\} da$$

For the high E limit, this is of the order $\ln(\sqrt{E})$ which is of the order $\ln(n)$, n being the energy level.

Correspondence Principle and WW

In quantum mechanics, $\text{Integral } dx \ WW=1$ regardless of the wavefunction. Out of curiosity, one may apply the correspondence principle i.e. $\text{density} = WW=C/v(x)$ where $v(x)$ is velocity to this problem. First, if one uses the spatial entropy form ((1)) $-2W \times dW/dx$, one should not use $1/v(x)$ with a derivative $d(WW)/dx$. The derivative must be applied to quantum humps and not to a smoothed $1/v(x)$ function and so $C/v(x)$ should only be substituted for WW which is not part of an x derivative. In this case: $\text{Integral } dx \ -2W \times dW/dx = \text{Integral } dx \ WW$ so $C/v(x)$ may be used in the latter. We wish to argue, however, that WW is not the spatial entropy density. It is merely a function whose overall spatial integral is the same as that of the actual spatial entropy density. Nevertheless, it is the full x integral which is calculated when finding the overall entropy.

Thus:

$$\text{Integral } dx \ WW = \text{Integral } dx \ C/v(x) = C \ \text{Integral } dx \ [2m(E-.5kxx)]^{1/2} \quad ((4))$$

If one uses the substitution $\sqrt{k/2} x = \sqrt{E} \sin(a)$, one finds that $E=hw(n+.5)$ cancels from ((4)) leaving an integral independent of E. Thus, the same result holds for all E which is analogous to $\text{Integral } dx \ WW = 1$ for all wavefunctions.

Spatial and Momentum Entropy Portions

Given that the x integral of $-2W \times dW/dx$ is 1 for all wavefunctions, it seems this spatial entropy density is only useful as a density. Usually in thermodynamics, one does not use entropy densities, but rather utilizes the full entropy. For the case of ((1)), the full entropy density depends on the momentum entropy portion as well. For the oscillator case, $a(p)$ the momentum wavefunction is a Gaussian just like the spatial $W(x)$. Thus, the correspondence approach

described above may be used to evaluate the momentum portion of entropy. In (1), the expression for the momentum portion is the same as ours if $a(p)=a(-p)$ as it does for some n of the oscillator. Thus, our momentum portion is:

$$S(\text{momentum}) = [-C_n C_n \int de H_n(e) H_n(e) \exp(-ee) \ln\{C_n C_n H_n(e) H_n(e) \exp(-ee)\} de + \ln(\sqrt{\hbar m})] \quad ((5))$$

where $H_n(e)$ is the n th Hermite polynomial. The above integral may be solved using: $C_n C_n H_n(e) H_n(e) \exp(-ee) = C/v(x)$ and yields $.5 \ln\{3.14 * 3.14 * \hbar * (n+.5)/2mw\}$ as shown in (1) where $w=\sqrt{k/m}$, k being the spring constant and n the energy level. Thus, in our case:

$$S_{\text{oscillator}} = 1 + \{ .5 \ln[3.14 * 3.14 * \hbar * (n+.5)/2mw] + \ln(mw) \} \quad ((6))$$

In the high n limit this is $S_{\text{oscillator high } n} = .5 \ln[3.14 * 3.14 * \hbar * (n+.5)/2mw]$

And the result from (1) is:

$$S_{\text{oscillator}} = \ln(\hbar) - \ln\{3.14 * 3.14 * \hbar * (n+.5)/2mw\} \quad ((7))$$

In the high n limit this is $-\ln\{3.14 * 3.14 * \hbar * (n+.5)/2mw\}$

Thus, our result in the high n limit differs from that of (1) by a factor of .5 because in our case there is no $\ln(n)$ contribution from the spatial entropy portion.

The results are close and the overall entropy of the oscillator for high n goes as $\ln(n)$, but the spatial entropies are very different in the two cases.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we compare an entropy expression ((1)) which we proposed in (2) with $-WW \ln(WW) - a(p)a(p)\ln[a(p)a(p)]$ used in (1) for the case of the oscillator. We find that the spatial parts are completely different. In our case, the spatial entropy is 1 regardless of the wavefunction. The momentum parts are similar, however, for the oscillator and so overall both entropies go as $\ln(n)$, but for different reasons. Furthermore, our result is .5 as large as that of (1) even in the high n limit.

References

1. Majernik, V and Opatrny Entropic Uncertainty Relations For a Quantum Oscillator (J. Phys. A Math 1996) <http://www.ktf.upol.cz/tom/clanky/jpa96-ent.pdf>
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